

D3.1 Interactive online map of the EU cybersecurity landscape

Methodological note

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EITD	EIT DIGITAL, COcyber coordinator leading project management (WP1) and synergies (WP6).
EOS	The European Organisation for Security, COcyber partner leading Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres (WP2).
LC	The Lisbon Council, COcyber partner leading Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform (WP3).
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
AUS	AUSTRALO marketing lab, COcyber partner leading communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement (WP5).
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.

Abbreviation	Description
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
WP	Work Package, form the COcyber working process.
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
CSIDB	Cyber Security Incident Database
CSIS	Center for Strategic & International Studies
DIANA	Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
EU	European Union
GCI	Global Cybersecurity Index
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation

1. Overview

The interactive online map of the EU cybersecurity is focused on addressing the collection and categorisation of a fragmented and widely dispersed set of existing cybersecurity intelligence and public information. It focuses on several critical areas to provide a comprehensive overview of cybersecurity developments and dynamics within the EU and beyond. The interactive online map serves as a tool for various stakeholders—businesses, policymakers, military, researchers, and cybersecurity professionals—by consolidating and categorising fragmented cybersecurity intelligence across the EU and other associated countries. It provides access to collective knowledge and information on cybersecurity, highlights existing modes of cooperation and funding opportunities, and identifies potential external factors influencing the EU cybersecurity landscape. Additionally, the online map will contribute to the Observatory, an online platform for the community (WP3), fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing across sectors.

The map is available here: <https://cocyper.eu/platform/cocyber-map>

Indicators integrated into the interactive Map:

Tender data indicators: these indicators offer insights into the dynamics of the cybersecurity procurement market. They highlight trends in the demand for cybersecurity solutions and services, revealing which sectors are making the largest investments. For governmental and institutional buyers, these indicators help evaluate the effectiveness of procurement policies and guide strategic decision-making.

Cyberskills data from Eurobarometer: this survey-based data focuses on the awareness, availability, and proficiency of digital and cybersecurity skills across the EU. It provides valuable insights into the current state of cybersecurity skills, helping identify gaps and areas requiring capacity-building efforts.

Project fund data indicators: these indicators provide financial insights into how resources are allocated and spent on cybersecurity initiatives. They help assess the effectiveness of investments, guide strategic decisions, and support policy evaluation by showcasing funding patterns and their impact on cybersecurity advancements.

2. Scope

This document serves as the methodological note outlining the purpose, structure, and key features of the Interactive online map of the EU Cybersecurity landscape. The map provides a comprehensive and dynamic visualisation of the cybersecurity ecosystem within the European Union and beyond, enabling users to explore key data and relationships across different countries.

The data integrated into the online map has been gathered from a range of open data sources, ensuring a broad and accurate representation of the cybersecurity landscape. The methodology behind the data collection and data consolidations will be detailed in this note to provide full transparency on the underlying process. This document aims to guide users in understanding the structure of the online map, the types of data it incorporates, and the insights it provides into the EU's cybersecurity environment. Through this map, stakeholders will gain valuable access to up-to-date, relevant information on the EU's cybersecurity domain.

3. Mapping and validation of data sources for the interactive online map

For this project, three types of indicators have been established to comprehensively assess the cybersecurity landscape and its dual-use applications, categorised according to their data sources:

- **Indicators based on publicly available data:** These indicators are derived from existing, openly accessible data sources. They provide a broad, standardised view of the cybersecurity environment across different countries, regions, and sectors.
- **Inside-Out indicators based on the survey data collected for needs assessment analysis of the COcyber project:** These indicators are generated from primary data collected through surveys targeting cybersecurity stakeholders, industry professionals, and organisations involved in cybersecurity. They reflect internal perceptions, needs, and gaps identified directly from the respondents, offering valuable insights into real-world challenges and priorities.

- Outside-In Indicators based on established frameworks from ENISA and NATO:** This category leverages existing frameworks, guidelines, and databases developed by authoritative organisations such as the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) and NATO. These indicators help to map the cybersecurity landscape across both civilian and defence sectors.

The limitations of the provided data sources are outlined below:

First type (Public data-based indicators):

While numerous cybersecurity indicators are available in public datasets, there is a significant limitation in the availability of indicators specifically focused on dual-use applications that can serve both civilian and defence purposes. This restricts the depth of analysis in this area.

Second type (Survey-based inside-out indicators):

The accuracy and reliability of these indicators are highly dependent on the response rate and the quality of the survey data collected. Low participation or biased responses could limit the representativeness and validity of the insights derived from this data.

Third type (Framework-based outside-in indicators):

The primary challenge here is the sensitivity of the data and the willingness of organisations to share detailed cybersecurity information. Given the confidential nature of security frameworks, especially within NATO and similar bodies, access to comprehensive data may be restricted, limiting our ability to apply these indicators fully.

Below is a table listing the data sources that were identified based on their relevance to the cybersecurity topic. While these sources were considered in the process, only those that met the specific requirements and objectives of this project were used for data gathering. This ensures that the selected data sources align with the project’s focus and provide the most relevant insights.

Data sources	Indicators (summary, coverage, public or private, framework or survey)	Indicator availability
Kaila	Kaila is an intelligent online platform designed to streamline innovation management by consolidating over 65 European public data sources into a single environment. While the exact list can evolve, some of the commonly known sources include: CORDIS, Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 databases, Eurostat, European Innovation Scoreboard, EU Open Data Portal, ESPON, National funding agencies and ministries and others. Indicators derived from project fund data in cybersecurity provide valuable financial insights into	available

Data sources	Indicators (summary, coverage, public or private, framework or survey)	Indicator availability
	resource allocation and utilisation. These indicators are crucial for evaluating investment effectiveness, guiding strategic decision-making, and supporting policy assessment. This applies to the EU 27, leveraging public data and digital services platforms.	
Eurobarometer	The Eurobarometer is a series of public opinion surveys conducted regularly on behalf of the European Commission. The public survey collects data regarding cybersecurity, employees, training needs, SMEs cybercrime, and cyber skills of 27 EU countries.	available
Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS)	The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) is the European Commission's primary platform for disseminating information on EU-funded research and innovation projects. It covers various domains, including cybersecurity, defence, and related sectors.	available
International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)	The public survey data offers a global overview of valid certificates, sectors, and sites across various countries, focusing on key sectors such as Public Administration, Education, Health and Social Work, and Other Social Services. It details the number of valid certificates issued, the sectors they cover, and the number of sites where organisations are operating under these certificates, providing insights into the global adoption of certified standards in these critical areas.	available
Shodan	Shodan is a world public search engine that scans the internet for connected devices, helping cybersecurity professionals identify vulnerabilities. It is used for securing networks, research, and monitoring IoT devices.	available
EU Funding Dashboard	The European Commission's Horizon Dashboard is a public platform that tracks EU-funded research and innovation, including cybersecurity projects, providing data on funding distributions across the EU27 to support innovation and collaboration.	available
Eurostat	Eurostat is the statistical office of the European Union, providing high-quality, reliable statistical data on Europe. Eurostat's data on the digital economy provides access to a wide range of statistics and reports. This includes information on the adoption of digital technologies, e-commerce, cybersecurity, and digital skills across EU countries.	available

Data sources	Indicators (summary, coverage, public or private, framework or survey)	Indicator availability
NCSI Project Team e-Governance Academy	National Cyber Security Index 3.0 evaluates if countries in the world have created a comprehensive and coordinated strategy for cybersecurity. It looks at key aspects such as strong leadership, the development of policies, coordination efforts, and the presence of a clear national cybersecurity strategy.	available
International Telecommunication Union (ITU)	The Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI) is a trusted tool that evaluates countries' commitment to cybersecurity by assessing their development in five key areas: Legal Measures, Technical Measures, Organisational Measures, Capacity Development, and Cooperation. This multi-stakeholder initiative aims to raise awareness of cybersecurity's importance and foster international cooperation and knowledge exchange. The GCI is based on the ITU Global Cybersecurity Agenda (GCA), which provides the framework for this initiative and involves various organisations to enhance the survey's quality and effectiveness.	not available
World Bank	The World Bank databases provide comprehensive global data on economic, social, and financial indicators. In the area of cybersecurity, the World Bank's data resources focus on assessing digital infrastructure, measuring cybersecurity readiness, and supporting policy development. The survey of World Bank examines the use of encrypted transactions through extensive automated exploration, tallying the number of websites using HTTPS.	available
Cyber Capacity Building (Cybil)	A repository of past and present international cyber capacity-building projects	available
Joint Research Centre (JRC)	The JRC's work on cybersecurity and other topics supports EU policies across various sectors in the European Union, with a focus on ensuring the security of digital infrastructures and systems within EU member states.	available
European Repository of Cyber Incidents (EuRepoC)	An independent research consortium delivering evidence-based analysis of cyber incidents to enhance understanding of the evolving cyber threat landscape.	available
Adversarial Tactics, Techniques and Common Knowledge (MITRE ATT&CK)	A global knowledge base framework of adversary tactics and techniques derived from real-world observations.	available

Data sources	Indicators (summary, coverage, public or private, framework or survey)	Indicator availability
Cyber Operations Tracker	A database of publicly documented state-sponsored cyber incidents since 2005.	available
Cyber Events Database by the Centre for International and Security Studies	Combines automation and manual review to structure data from open sources on publicly attributed attacks.	available
Cyber Security Incident Database (CSIDB)	An open-source threat intelligence platform for cybersecurity professionals, featuring a curated incident database.	available
Operational Technology Cyber Attack Database (OTCAD)	A public database of cyberattacks on operational technology and industrial control systems, aligned with MITRE's ATT&CK for ICS.	available
COcyber survey	A survey regarding coordination between the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres in EU 27 countries	available
European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)	EU agency that enhances cybersecurity across Europe by providing expertise, supporting risk management, incident response, and policy development. It promotes collaboration among EU countries, supports cybersecurity certification, and helps address emerging digital threats.	not publicly available
North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO)	Cybersecurity for both European and non-European countries, treating cyberattacks as a serious threat It collaborates through joint exercises, information sharing, and the Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence in Estonia, while supporting global training and resources for members and partners.	not publicly available
Opentender	A public procurement data platform for the EU 27 provides access to tender data, contract, and bid information across member states. It offers insights into trends and investments in various sectors, including cybersecurity. This data helps assess demand, monitor procurement policies, and guide decision-making for both government buyers and suppliers across Europe.	available
Center For Strategic & International Studies (CSIS)	A timeline of major world cyber incidents since 2006, highlighting state actions, espionage, and cyberattacks with significant losses.	available
CYBER READINESS INDEX 2.0	The CRI 2.0 assesses a country's cybersecurity maturity and commitment, guiding national leaders in protecting digital economies and fostering GDP growth. It also	not publicly available

Data sources	Indicators (summary, coverage, public or private, framework or survey)	Indicator availability
	provides a structured blueprint for achieving "cyber readiness," outlining the key components needed to enhance cybersecurity and resilience.	
Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic (DIANA)	It tracks global innovation hubs, technologies, and partners involved in NATO's Defence Innovation Accelerator for the North Atlantic (DIANA) program. This initiative focuses on advancing emerging technologies to enhance defence and security, including areas like AI, robotics, and cybersecurity.	available

Table 1 Indicators Data source

4. List of indicators implemented in the interactive online map

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
<p>Indicators based on tender data offer valuable insights into the dynamics of the cybersecurity procurement market. They help identify trends in the demand for cybersecurity solutions and services, highlighting which sectors are making the largest investments. For government or institutional buyers, these indicators serve as a tool to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity procurement policies and guide decision-making.</p>			
<p>Share of tender budgets across participating countries, %</p>	<p>Measures the proportion of the total allocated budget for tenders distributed among different participating countries. Helps in assessing how tender funds are distributed geographically.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27, associated countries, Norway (NO), Iceland (IS), Switzerland (CH), Georgia (GE), Serbia (RS), North Macedonia (MK). No data is available for LT. CY and SI are missing. Period: 2014–2025</p>	<p>Opentender</p>
<p>Share of tenders per country, %</p>	<p>Measures the proportion of total tenders (e.g., procurement opportunities, bids, or contracts) that are</p>	<p>Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK.</p>	<p>Opentender</p>

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
	associated with each country. It provides insight into the level of tender activity in each country.	CY, and SI are missing. Period: 2014-2025	
Share of tender budget per million people, (€)	Measures how much of the total tender budget is allocated per one million inhabitants in each country. This indicator helps compare the relative investment or funding distribution across countries, considering population differences.	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. No data is available for LT. CY and SI are missing. Period: 2014-2025	Opentender
Average tender size, (€)	Measures the average budget allocated to tenders by country. Provides valuable insights into the scale or magnitude of tenders.	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. No data is available for LT. CY and SI are missing. Period: 2014-2025	Opentender
Tender size benchmark: <i>Above threshold tender size benchmark, %</i> <i>Below threshold tender size benchmark, %</i>	Refers to a reference point or standard used to compare and assess the size of tenders.	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. No data is available for ES, HU, IL, LT, LU, MK, RO, RS. CY and SI are missing. Period: 2014-2025	Opentender
Supply type distribution: Services distribution, % Supplies distribution, % Works distribution, %	Measures the proportion of different types of supplies, goods, or services that are being procured or tendered. Provides insight into market demand trends.	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. No data is available for LV. CY and SI are missing.	Opentender

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
		Period: 2014–2025	
Buyer organisation type, %	Categories the organisations that are issuing tenders or procurement opportunities based on their type. The indicator is presented in an aggregated form for all countries. (chart type visualisation)	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. No data is available for BE, BG, FI, GR, LV, RO, RS. CY and SI are missing. Period: 2014–2025	Opentender
Main activities of buyers, %	Describes the key activities or functions carried out by the organisations that issue tenders or procurement opportunities. The indicator is presented in an aggregated form for all countries. (chart type visualisation)	Coverage EU27, associated countries, NO, IS, CH, GE, RS, MK. CY, and SI are missing. Period: 2014–2025	Opentender
Cyberskills data from Eurobarometer is a survey-based data collected by the Eurobarometer, focusing on the awareness, availability, and proficiency of digital and cybersecurity skills across the EU. It provides insights into the state of cybersecurity skills across the EU.			
Cybersecurity workforce within companies: <i>Share of companies employing at least one Cybersecurity professionals, %</i>	Measures the share of companies that employ at least one employee within a company who holds positions or performs roles directly related to cybersecurity, providing insight into the organisation's capacity to defend against cyber threats.	Coverage EU27 Period: 2024	Eurobarometer
Pathways to cybersecurity employment: <i>Share of companies recruited employees from non-cybersecurity roles, %</i> <i>Share of companies recruited employees from a previous role in cyber security, %</i>	Measures how employees currently involved in cybersecurity roles within a company entered their positions. It helps identify the most common routes into cybersecurity roles, offering insights into workforce	Coverage EU27 Period: 2024	Eurobarometer

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
<p><i>Share of companies integrating Cybersecurity roles into existing non-Cybersecurity positions, %</i> <i>Share of companies recruiting employees as career starters (e.g., Graduates), %</i></p>	<p>development trends and talent acquisition strategies.</p>		
<p>Cybersecurity skills gap in hiring: <i>Share of enterprises having some difficulties in hiring staff with appropriate cybersecurity skills, %</i> <i>Share of enterprises having no difficulties in hiring staff with appropriate cybersecurity skills, %</i></p>	<p>Measures the level of challenge companies face in finding and hiring staff with the appropriate cybersecurity skills.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27 Period: 2024</p>	<p>Eurobarometer</p>
<p>Cybersecurity recruitment challenges: <i>Share of companies reporting difficulties finding qualified Cybersecurity candidates, %</i> <i>Share of companies citing lack of applicants for cybersecurity roles, %</i> <i>Share of companies mentioning budget constraints in cybersecurity recruitment, %</i> <i>Share of companies challenged by rapidly changing cybersecurity technologies, %</i> <i>Share of companies citing the need for continuous cybersecurity training, %</i> <i>Share of companies mentioning the security clearance requirements in cybersecurity hiring, %</i> <i>Share of companies mentioning the competing environment for cybersecurity talent, %</i> <i>Share of companies mentioning lack of awareness about cybersecurity roles, %</i> <i>Share of companies struggling to manage cybersecurity staff turnover, %</i></p>	<p>Identifies the key obstacles organisations face when trying to recruit staff with the appropriate cybersecurity skills. This indicator helps highlight specific barriers in the cybersecurity talent acquisition process.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27 Period: 2024</p>	<p>Eurobarometer</p>
<p>Cybersecurity talent demand: <i>Share of companies reporting at least one Cybersecurity position (FTE) needing to be filled, %</i></p>	<p>Helps to understand the scale of the cybersecurity staffing needs.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27 Period: 2024</p>	<p>Eurobarometer</p>

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
<p>Top in-demand Cybersecurity positions:</p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking chief security/information officer as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking emergency and crisis management expert as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking procurement experts most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking security inspector, auditor as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking legal compliance expert as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking security training expert as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking digital forensic investigator as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking incident response handler as most important role, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies ranking Cyber security researcher as most important role, %</i></p>	<p>Helps to determine which cybersecurity roles are essential for safeguarding their systems and data. The positions can be prioritised in terms of hiring, training, and investment.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27 Period: 2024</p>	<p>Eurobarometer</p>
<p>Most critical Cybersecurity skills:</p> <p><i>Share of companies prioritising social engineering as key skill, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies prioritising code, script, and program development skills, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies focusing on data protection and privacy practices, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies emphasising cyber threat information collection and analysis, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies prioritising development of security and privacy requirements, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies focusing on software/hardware security analysis and review, %</i></p> <p><i>Share of companies identifying cybersecurity awareness, training, and education needs, %</i></p>	<p>Helps to assess the skills gap in the cybersecurity workforce and prioritise efforts in developing, recruiting, or training the necessary skills to address the most important cybersecurity challenges they face.</p>	<p>Coverage EU27 Period: 2024</p>	<p>Eurobarometer</p>

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
<i>Share of companies prioritising integration of cybersecurity solutions, %</i> <i>Share of companies focusing on identification and resolution of cybersecurity issues, %</i>			
<p>Indicators based on project fund data in the cybersecurity domain provide valuable financial insights into how resources are allocated and spent on cybersecurity initiatives. These indicators help assess the effectiveness of investments, guide strategic decision-making, and support policy evaluation.</p>			
Share of Cybersecurity projects across participating countries, %	Measures the distribution of cybersecurity projects among participating countries.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila ¹
Share of Cybersecurity projects granted per year for all EU countries, %	Represents the annual distribution of granted cybersecurity projects across all countries, providing an overview of the	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is	Kaila

¹Here is a list of multiple data sources collected by Kaila that provide relevant information on cybersecurity-related projects:

- Latvia-Lithuania Programme (2014-2020) – 2014-2020.latlit.eu
- Central Baltic Programme – centralbaltic.eu
- CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service) – cordis.europa.eu
- European Commission (EC) Data Portal – ec.europa.eu
- EEA Grants – eeagrants.org
- GroupSpaces (Collaboration Platform) – groupspaces.com
- Interreg Baltic Sea Region – interreg-baltic.eu
- Interreg Central Europe – interreg-core.eu
- KEEP (Interreg Project Database) – keep.eu
- Alpine Space Programme – www.alpine-space.eu
- ESPON (European Spatial Planning Observation Network) – www.espon.eu
- Eurostars Programme (EUREKA Network) – www.eurostars-eureka.eu
- Interreg Danube Transnational Programme – www.interreg-danube.eu
- Interreg France-Wallonia-Flanders – www.interreg-fwvl.eu
- Interreg (General EU Interregional Cooperation Programmes) – www.interreg.org
- Interreg Aurora Programme – www.interregaurora.eu
- Interreg Europe – www.interregeurope.eu
- Interreg Nord Programme – www.interregnord.com
- Interreg IPA CBC Bulgaria-Serbia – www.ipacbc-bgrs.eu
- Interreg Italy-Slovenia Programme – www.ita-slo.eu
- Interreg Italy-Croatia Programme – www.italy-croatia.eu
- Interreg Lithuania-Poland Programme – www.lietuva-polska.eu
- North Sea Region Programme (Interreg) – www.northsearegion.eu
- Paramount Project (EU-funded initiative) – www.paramount-project.eu
- Interreg Spain-Portugal (POCTEP) Programme – www.poctep.es

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
	evolving cybersecurity landscape. (chart type visualisation)	available for 2006–2007 period	
Share of budgets granted for Cybersecurity projects across participating countries, %	Measures the proportion of the total allocated budget for projects distributed among different participating countries. Helps in assessing how project funds are distributed geographically.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Share of Cybersecurity projects budget per million people, (€)	Measures how much of the total project budget is allocated per one million inhabitants in each country. This indicator helps compare the relative investment or funding distribution across countries, considering population differences.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Average project size by country, (€)	Measures the average budget allocated to projects by country, offering valuable insights into their scale and scope.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Top 10 programs funding the projects, %	Identifies and categorises the various funding programs or initiatives that provide financial support for projects in cybersecurity domain. The indicator is presented in an aggregated form for all countries. (chart type visualisation)	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Status of the projects for the whole period, %	Provide a comprehensive view of the progress and outcomes of projects over their entire lifecycle for all countries. The indicator is presented in an aggregated	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for	Kaila

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
	form for all countries. (chart type visualisation)	2006–2007 period	
Status of the project per country: <i>Closed projects per country, %</i> <i>Ongoing projects per country, %</i>	Provide a comprehensive view of the progress and outcomes of projects over their entire lifecycle per country.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Share of budget granted for Cybersecurity projects per year, %	Measures the proportion of the total allocated budget for projects distributed among all countries per year. The indicator is presented in an aggregated form for all countries. (chart type visualisation)	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Share of budgets granted for Cybersecurity projects per type of the participant: <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to NGOs, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to other organisations, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to private companies, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to public entities, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to research institutions, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to SMEs, %</i> <i>Share of budgets granted for cybersecurity projects to Universities, %</i>	Measures the proportion of total funding allocated to different types of participants involved in cybersecurity projects. It breaks down the distribution of cybersecurity project budgets across various participant categories, such as NGOs, private companies, public entities, research institutions, SMEs, and universities. Provides a clear view of how cybersecurity project funding is distributed among different organisations.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila
Share of participant types receiving grants for Cybersecurity projects: <i>Share of NGOs receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i>	Measures the proportion of different participant groups (such as NGOs, private companies, public entities, research institutions, SMEs, and universities) that receive	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for	Kaila

Indicator	Indicator definition and purpose	Overview	Source
<i>Share of other organisations receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i> <i>Share of private companies receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i> <i>Share of public entities receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i> <i>Share of research institutions receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i> <i>Share of SMEs receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i> <i>Share of universities receiving grants for cybersecurity projects, %</i>	financial support or grants for cybersecurity-related projects.	2006–2007 period	
Average project size per participant types: <i>Average project size for NGOs, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for other participants, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for private companies, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for public entities, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for research institutions, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for SMEs, (€)</i> <i>Average project size for universities, (€)</i>	Measures the average budget allocated to projects, categorised by different types of participants. Provides valuable insights into the scale or magnitude of projects.	Coverage EU27 and other non-EU countries Period:2005–2025, No data is available for 2006–2007 period	Kaila

Table 2 Indicators implemented in the interactive online map

Note: Indicators based on survey data for needs analysis in the civilian and defence sectors, which aim to assess specific needs, gaps, and priorities, are not included in the online map due to a low response rate. However, the survey will remain open for one year, and the online interactive map will be updated accordingly with survey-derived indicators and an accompanying methodological note.

5. Data consolidation and limitations

The data for the online interactive map has been consolidated from multiple reliable sources to provide a comprehensive overview of the EU cybersecurity landscape and beyond. This includes:

- Tender data: collected from public procurement platforms to track trends in cybersecurity solutions and service demands, highlighting sectors with significant investments.

- Cyberskills data: sourced from Eurobarometer surveys, offering insights into digital and cybersecurity skills' awareness, availability, and proficiency across EU Member States.
- Project fund data: compiled from funding databases and project reports, providing financial insights into resource allocation and spending on cybersecurity initiatives.

Two primary data sources, Kaila (project fund data) and Opentender (tender data), underwent several data processing steps to extract relevant information aligned with the project's objectives. Below is an outline of the data consolidation procedures performed for each source.

Kaila (project fund data):

To capture projects relevant to the cybersecurity domain, we implemented a customised search engine within the Kaila platform. The following keywords were utilised to filter the data:

"computer security", "security platform", "infrastructure security", "infrastructure protection", "network security", "network protection", "information security", "data protection", "information protection", "cybersecurity", and "cyber security".

Using these keywords, we initially identified 1,487 projects across the EU27 countries. However, a portion of these projects did not align with the specific focus of our study. To address this, we conducted a thorough data cleaning process, which involved: Irrelevant projects which not directly related to cybersecurity were excluded. Duplicate entries were identified and removed to ensure data accuracy.

After this refinement, the final dataset comprised 1,309 unique cybersecurity-related projects within the EU27.

Opentender (tender data):

A similar procedure was applied to the Opentender database to identify tenders relevant to the cybersecurity sector. Using the same set of keywords, we analysed tenders from 2014 to 2025, initially identifying 1,159 observations. The data was then processed to ensure relevance and accuracy:

- Any repeated entries were systematically eliminated.
- Tenders not directly related to cybersecurity solutions or services were excluded.

Following the cleaning process, the final dataset included 987 relevant tenders covering the EU27 countries, as well as associated countries and Norway (NO), Iceland (IS), Switzerland (CH), Georgia (GE), Serbia (RS), and North Macedonia (MK).

Limitations:

We have encountered several limitations in processing the data:

1. Keywords sensitivity: the reliance on specific keywords may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant projects or tenders that did not explicitly use these terms but were still pertinent to cybersecurity.
2. Scope of data: despite extensive cleaning, some irrelevant entries might persist, while certain relevant projects may have been unintentionally omitted.
3. Temporal coverage: data inconsistencies across different time periods may affect trend analysis, particularly for tenders extending into future years (up to 2025).